

Bias Introduced by Mean Orientation Estimation Methods

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ABSTRACT

Many problems deal with two-dimensional random variables. One of them concerns the estimation of statistical parameters from a gradient vector field on a 2D-lattice. Special interest has been devoted to the extraction of orientation on textures. Unfortunately, the computation of directional statistics may introduce anomalies and distortions in the statistical distribution of orientation measures. This article gives a theoretical explanation to this phenomenon and provides a possible answer to such a problem, based on the sub-sampling of the gradient orientation field.

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper lies within the scope of recent works on oriented texture fields [3][4][6]. In directional textures, orientation is an inevitable feature when characterizing the spatial organization of textural patterns like fingerprint minutiae [3] or seismic layers [1]. For 2-D images, the computation of local operators, like Sobel's gradient, supplies us with an orientation vector field.

Several authors are interested in studying the statistical distribution of this vector field. Within the framework of multi-scale anisotropy estimation, Germain [2] defines the directional tendency as an estimate of the orientation at a given scale. His approach consists in partitioning the 2-D gradient field into square windows and in computing a Directional Mean Vector for each window. Others compute mean orientations on sliding windows so as to smooth the orientation field and to get rid of noise, smudges or breaks in ridges [3]. In both cases, the orientation mean is computed on square windows. Let the window size be the observation scale.

Orientations are defined modulo π and classical statistics do not apply when dealing with such periodic data. A few methods allow to compute an accurate orientation mean. They are derived from the directional statistics of Mardia [5] and are based on the argument doubling.

However these statistical methods do not apply to non-independent random variables. Indeed the way the orientation is estimated results in a distribution of correlated vectors. Fig. 1a points out the overlapping of

Figure 1: Overlapping (a) and independent (b) masks.

3×3 masks for neighboring pixels. Our objective is to study how this overlapping leads to preferential orientations. Then we propose an alternative way to compute a directional tendency.

This paper is divided as follows: in section 2, after giving tools to estimate the local orientation, a general method will be presented in order to compute the statistical mean of an orientation in a square window. In section 3, through a theoretical approach, we will see how the gradient mask overlapping leads to preferential directions when computing a directional tendency, even in the case of a white Gaussian noise. Then, section 4 will present several simulations which reveal the distortion of the statistical distributions. At last, section 5 will provide a solution based on the sub-sampling of the local orientation field and avoiding this directional bias.

2 ESTIMATING AN ORIENTATION

2.1 Gradient Local Estimate

Let us represent a texture as a three-dimensional topographical surface. The local orientation is given by the tangent to the level curve i.e. the orthogonal direction to the gradient. The gradient vector gives two attributes: an orientation estimation and a modulus which stands for the surface slope. Sobel or Prewitt's filters are classically chosen in order to estimate the gradient because their 3×3 sized convolution masks make them local operators. Both are smoothed versions of the elementary *cross gradient* shown in Fig. 2a.

Figure 2: Cross gradient (a) and Sobel's gradient (b).

In fact Sobel and Prewitt's operators are hardly different since only the mask weighting coefficients differ. From now on, we will only study the behaviour of the cross gradient and Sobel's operator.

2.2 Directional Tendency

Various methods have been proposed to estimate the directional tendency of oriented textures [7]. The method we address is just one of the different implementations of Rao's algorithm [1][3][6]. It is based on the orientation vector field given by the gradient computation. Since orientations are π -periodic data, this periodicity must be taken into account in order to estimate a mean tendency. This is usually done by doubling the arguments of the gradient vectors when computing the average [5][7].

The algorithm is divided into three steps:

1. The gradient vector field $\{(g_{k,x}, g_{k,y})\}_{k=1..L^2}$ is computed on the whole $L \times L$ image.
2. Around each pixel, we define a $n = N \times N$ window, N being the observation scale.
3. Then, the mean orientation $\hat{\theta}$ is estimated on each of the L^2 windows of the whole image:

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \arctan\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i^2 \sin 2\theta_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i^2 \cos 2\theta_i}\right), \quad (1)$$

where (ρ_i, θ_i) are the polar coordinates of the i^{th} vector from the n -sized vector field of the current window.

The formula of Eq. 2 is preferred since it avoids the sine and cosine computation [1][3][4]:

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{2} \cdot \arctan\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n 2g_{i,x}g_{i,y}}{\sum_{i=1}^n (g_{i,x}^2 - g_{i,y}^2)}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $(g_{i,x}, g_{i,y})$ are the Cartesian coordinates of the i^{th} gradient vector.

In fact, the method consists in a vector sum of the gradients which had their arguments doubled and their moduli squared. $\sum_{i=1}^n (g_{i,x}^2 - g_{i,y}^2)$ and $\sum_{i=1}^n 2g_{i,x}g_{i,y}$ are the sum coordinates. $\hat{\theta}$ is just half the argument of the sum. In [2], the approach is quite similar: the ρ_i^2 weighting coefficients are just replaced by ρ_i in Eq. 1.

The study below will use the formulation of Eq. 2 since it proves to have a lower computational cost.

3 DIRECTIONAL ANISOTROPY

We will see below how the statistical method presented in section 2 leads to unexpected results when it is applied to non-independent data. But, first of all, let us verify the isotropy of the orientation measurement given by the gradient vector on a white gaussian noise image. The study is done with Sobel's operator.

3.1 Isotropy of the Gradient Estimate

Let consider a white gaussian noise image. The gray level on each pixel is a normally distributed random variable with standard deviation σ . Let ΔX , ΔY and Θ denote the random variables associated with the coordinates and the orientation of Sobel's gradient vector:

$$\Theta = \arctan \frac{\Delta Y}{\Delta X}.$$

Allowing a few developments, ΔX and ΔY prove to be independent, zero mean and normally distributed random variables with standard deviation $2\sqrt{2}\sigma$. Then $Z = \frac{\Delta Y}{\Delta X}$, being the quotient of two normally distributed variables, is Cauchy distributed:

$$p_Z(z) = \frac{1}{\pi(1+z^2)}.$$

At last, it can be shown easily that the arctan of a Cauchy distributed variable is uniform. So $p_\Theta(\theta) = \frac{1}{\pi}$, which means that all the orientations given by the gradient have the same probability.

3.2 Averaging and Anisotropy

For simplicity, let $\{(a_i, b_i) = (g_{i,x}, g_{i,y})\}_{i=1..n}$ denote the Cartesian coordinates of the gradient vectors.

$$\begin{cases} X_{res} &= \sum_{i=1..n} (a_i^2 - b_i^2) \\ Y_{res} &= \sum_{i=1..n} 2a_i b_i, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

are the coordinates of the vector sum. The argument of the vector (X_{res}, Y_{res}) is expected to be twice the orientation expectation. The covariance associated to the (X_{res}, Y_{res}) pair is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} Cov(X_{res}, Y_{res}) &= E(X_{res} \cdot Y_{res}) \\ &= 2 \cdot \sum_{i,k} E(a_i^2 a_k b_k) - E(b_i^2 a_k b_k). \end{aligned}$$

When dealing with a white noise, both Sobel and cross gradients lead to $E(a_i^2 a_k b_k) = E(b_i^2 a_k b_k) = 0$. Then,

$$Cov(X_{res}, Y_{res}) = 0. \quad (4)$$

The covariance does not show any dependency between the x and y coordinates.

However, the 2-D spatial distribution of the (X_{res}, Y_{res}) vector set happens to be anisotropic. Indeed the variance along the x -axis proves to be greater than the variance along the y -axis.

Let us develop an analytical formulation for these variances whatever the observation scale:

$$\begin{cases} E(X_{res}^2) &= E[\sum_{i=1}^n (a_i^2 - b_i^2) \cdot \sum_{k=1}^n (a_k^2 - b_k^2)] \\ E(Y_{res}^2) &= E[(\sum_{k=1}^n 2a_k b_k)^2] \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} E(X_{res}^2) &= \sum_{i,k} E(a_i^2 a_k^2 + b_i^2 b_k^2) - 2 \cdot \sum_{i,k} E(a_i^2 b_k^2) \\ E(Y_{res}^2) &= 4 \cdot \sum_{i,k} E(a_i b_i a_k b_k). \end{cases}$$

As in 3.1, we consider a white gaussian noise image. The gray level on each pixel is a normally distributed random variable with standard deviation σ . Using this probability function, we can get the expressions for the expectations $E(a_i^2 a_k^2 + b_i^2 b_k^2)$, $E(a_i^2 b_k^2)$ and $E(a_i b_i a_k b_k)$ where i and k are the locations of the masks studied. Several configurations of the couple of masks have to

$d_{i,k}$	$E(a_i^2 a_k^2) + E(b_i^2 b_k^2)$	$E(a_i^2 b_k^2)$	$E(a_i b_i a_k b_k)$	Card
$d_{i,k} = 0$	$864\sigma^4$	$144\sigma^4$	$576\sigma^4$	n^2
$d_{i,k} = 1$ 	$416\sigma^4$	$144\sigma^4$	0	$4n^2 - 4n$
$d_{i,k} = \sqrt{2}$ 	$288\sigma^4$	$176\sigma^4$	$16\sigma^4$	$4n^2 - 8n + 4$
$d_{i,k} = 2$ 	$368\sigma^4$	$144\sigma^4$	$-12\sigma^4$	$4n^2 - 8n$
$d_{i,k} = \sqrt{5}$ 	$320\sigma^4$	$152\sigma^4$	$4\sigma^4$	$8n^2 - 24n + 16$
$d_{i,k} = \sqrt{8}$ 	$292\sigma^4$	$146\sigma^4$	$2\sigma^4$	$4n^2 - 16n + 16$
$d_{i,k} \geq 3$	0	0	0	0

Table 1: Elements for the calculus of the variances in the case of Sobel's gradient.

be considered depending on the geodesic Cartesian distance $d_{i,k}$ between them: the masks can be either equal, independent or partially dependent. The configurations obtained with Sobel's gradient and the corresponding values for the expectations are listed in Table 1. The cardinality of each configuration is also given.

Using Table 1, we get the expressions for the above variances as a function of σ and of the scale N :

$$\begin{cases} E(X_{res}^2) &= (1280N^2 - 1024N) \cdot \sigma^4 \\ E(Y_{res}^2) &= (632N^2 - 160N + 160) \sigma^4. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

We can see that $E(X_{res}^2) > E(Y_{res}^2), \forall N \geq 2$. So, the x -variance is greater than the y -variance, i.e. the set of

(X_{res}, Y_{res}) vectors spans rather horizontally, allowing two preferential directions: 0 and π radians. Dividing these orientations by two leads to a $0-\frac{\pi}{2}$ bi-modal distribution as we will see below (Fig. 3e).

For information, the cross gradient calculation yields:

$$\begin{cases} E(X_{res}^2) &= (8N^2 + 16N - 16) \cdot \sigma^4 \\ E(Y_{res}^2) &= 16N^2 \sigma^4. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here $E(Y_{res}^2) > E(X_{res}^2)$. Then the (X_{res}, Y_{res}) vector field spans rather vertically than horizontally which brings the $\frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{3\pi}{4}$ preferential directions (Fig. 3g).

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Fig. 3a consists of a white gaussian noise. If we compute Sobel's operator on the whole set of pixels, we can draw the $0-\pi$ distribution of the gradient orientations given in Fig. 3c. We can see that this distribution is uniform.

Figure 3: (a) White gaussian noise image, (b) noisy oriented plane, (c) and (d) $0-\pi$ distribution of Sobel's orientations computed on a and b, (e) and (f) 9×9 mean orientation distribution computed on a and b using Sobel's gradient, (g) and (h) corresponding 9×9 mean orientation distribution using the cross gradient.

Any average computed on a set of random orientations is expected to take a random value between

0 and π . On the contrary, when computing the mean orientations on 9×9 windows, we obtain a bi-modal distribution (see Fig. 3e). Two orientations predominate: 0 and $\frac{\pi}{2}$, which confirms the theoretical results of the previous section.

Let us now consider an inclined plane contaminated by a white gaussian noise (Fig. 3b). Its local orientation distribution is centered around the theoretical texture direction θ_{theo} (Fig. 3d). But the mean orientation distribution is distorted: the mode is shifted on the right towards $\frac{\pi}{2}$ (Fig. 3f). In fact, the mode is shifted either towards 0 or $\frac{\pi}{2}$ depending on the smaller distance from each preferential direction to the theoretical direction.

The same simulations using the cross gradient lead to the mean orientation distributions given on Fig. 3g and 3h. Here, the preferential directions are $\frac{\pi}{4}$ and $\frac{3\pi}{4}$. Moreover, when dealing with the noisy inclined plane, the cross gradient method is even more sensitive than Sobel's method as the $\frac{3\pi}{4}$ mode also appears.

5 PARTITION INTO NINE CODINGS

We have seen above that a linear statistical operation, like a directional mean, leads to a distortion of the mean orientation distribution and eventually to a bias in the mean estimation. This is due to the mask overlapping when dealing with the complete grid of pixels.

The solution we propose is based on the partition of the orientation grid into disjoint sets called codings. The orientations making up each coding are independent. Nine codings are needed so that 3×3 neighborhoods do not interfere. Estimating a mean orientation in a given window consists in computing Eq. 2 on the pixels of the window which belong to the same coding.

Figure 4: Partition of the grid into 9 codings.

This method guarantees the isotropy of the estimation on a white noise image (see Fig. 5a): the results, given on Fig. 5c, show a uniform distribution similar to the one obtained before averaging. In the case of an oriented image, it leads to an unbiased estimation: Fig. 5d shows the 9×9 mean orientation distribution computed on Fig. 3b. No distortion of the mode is observed. However, this distribution suffers a greater variance to noise since less local estimations are used to compute the mean tendency.

Figure 5: (a) and (b) 9×9 Sobel based mean orientation distribution computed respectively on Fig. 3 (a) and (b) using one of the nine codings.

6 CONCLUSION

In this paper we presented a gradient-based technique for mean orientation retrieval. This technique uses classical operators like Sobel's gradient, computed on the entire grid of pixels. Through several experiments, involving mean estimates on overlapping windows, it proved to be biased due to the dependency of the computed data. In the case of a white noise image, a statistical study of the mean orientation distribution explained this bias phenomenon. The sub-sampling method we proposed here uses a set of nine codings of the gradient vector field. It avoids the gradient mask overlapping and then guarantees the independence of data. No bias is introduced, even if the sensitivity to noise is increased.

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